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Content Validity Analysis Of An Alternative Biology Practical Skills Assessment Tool Among Secondary School Students In Taraba State, Nigeria

Prof. Amuche, Christian Igomu¹; Dr. Obiji, Donatus² & Sam, Kurutsi Danazumi³

^{1,2,3}Department of Educational Foundations,
Taraba State University Jalingo, Nigeria

³Email: samkurutsi@gmail.com (Corresponding Author)

ABSTRACT

The study was undertaken to carry out content validity analysis of an alternative Biology practical skills assessment tool among secondary school students in Taraba State, Nigeria. The study adopted the instrumentation design. The population for the study was 15,142 from 346 secondary schools. The sample for the study was 1,013 senior secondary school II (SSS II) students. Stratified purposive sampling technique was used and a 162 psycho-productive test known as Practical Skills Assessment Test (P-SAT) was developed and analyzed by the study. Content validity ratio which was estimated from the ratings of 10 experts, showed that the instrument averagely has an excellent ratio of 0.93. A few items showed content validity index of 0.80. This suggested that they are still acceptable and relevant. The result of analysis indicated that majority of items meet the recommended content validity ratio threshold of 0.78. It was therefore recommended that Biology teachers in Taraba State should use P-SAT as a valid question bank for future assessment of practical skills among students in secondary schools across Taraba State. It was also recommended that school authorities, administrators and test experts should train and encourage teachers to make use of the procedure adopted in this study to enable them to carry out validity analysis on test items for assessment of practical skills of secondary school students in Taraba State.

Keywords: Validity; Content Validity; Practical Skill Assessment Test (P-SAT)

INTRODUCTION

Biology laboratory activity as asserted in Agu and Iyamu (2018), is an important aspect of learning of Biology because it equips a student to develop practical skills in solving problems. Laboratory activity, as stated by Asamoah and Aboagye (2019), forms an integral part of learning and provides aid for performance assessment as enshrined in the Biology syllabus designed for senior secondary schools. This could foster proper understanding of Biology concepts as well as ability for its application in the resolution and management of social, economic and environmental problems for the much desired technological advancement and all round development of our nation (Olabimtan, 2015 & 2016; Babajide & Peter, 2021). Performance-based assessment measures students' ability to apply the skills and knowledge learned. Typically, the task challenges students to use their higher-order thinking skills to create a product or complete a process. These activities usually employ the use of Biology equipment, apparatuses and other instructional materials for utilization by students during assessment of Biology (Hilliard, 2015; Josiah & Gana, 2019).

Despite the importance of Biology activity-based assessment which accords secondary school students the opportunity to acquire skills for application in industry and a vast number of other professions, teaching and assessment of practical Biology in secondary schools in Nigeria has continue to be fraught with challenges of inadequate laboratory apparatuses causing Biology assessment to fall short of their skill assessment expectation (Josiah & Gana, 2019). There has been a tremendous growth in students' population without a corresponding growth in the number of facilities for assessment of skills as a result of economic depression and corresponding rise in cost as suggested by Osuji (2016). The absence of these facilities often leave teachers and test experts in a state of inactivity as they find it difficult or practically impossible to improvise (Babajide & Peter, 2021). This lack of functional Biology laboratory and inadequate equipment for Biology practical in most Nigerian secondary schools as stressed by Aderonmu and Obafemi (2015), is hampering laboratory activities and assessment of skills. In today's Nigeria, therefore, where secondary schools are fraught with challenges of lack of facilities for assessment of Biology practical skills, a valid and reliable assessment Test (P-SAT), therefore, becomes a necessary alternative.

P-SAT use Simpson's Taxonomy with perception, set, guided response, mechanism, complex overt response, adaptation and origination as its psychomotor domain levels. It uses multiple choice questions and typically requires Biology students to select a correct answer from a list of alternatives. Usually, a single correct answer is randomly placed among several other wrong options. This means only one alternative is correct, whereas other alternatives are incorrect (Abraham & Connor, 2020; McKenna, 2018; Sharma, 2021). Validity analysis is one of the most important aspects of test construction. A good test development process must ensure that a test is valid. Validity as stated by Kubai (2019), forms the psychometric properties of measurement scales that are very important in estimating adequacy and accuracy procedures of a scientific research.

Validation is an important process which ensures that a developed instrument is able to measure what it intends to measure (DeVellis, 2017). A test has face validity if its content simply looks relevant to the test takers it is meant for. It evaluates the appearance of an instrument in terms of feasibility, readability, consistency of style and formatting, and the clarity of the language used. It is the subjective assessments of the presentation and relevance of a measuring instrument as to whether the items in the instrument appear to be relevant, reasonable, unambiguous and clear (Taherdoost, 2016; Ramli et al., 2020). Content validity, as a type of validity, explains the degree to which items in an instrument reflects the content area to which an instrument can be generalized. It involves evaluation of a new instrument in order to ensure that it includes all the items that are essential and eliminate undesirable items to a particular construct domain.

Construct validity refers to how well you translated or transformed a concept, idea, or behaviour that is a construct into a functioning and operating reality, the operationalization. The two components of construct validity are convergent and discriminant validity. While discriminant validity explains the extent to which a latent variable discriminates from other latent variables, convergent validity describes the degree to which two measures of constructs that theoretically should be related are, in fact, related and this could be estimated through a diligent process of item analysis (Taherdoost, 2016). Therefore, in order to assess students in both process and product skills, P-SAT was developed and validated.

Statement of the Problem

Over the years, there has been a tremendous growth in students' population without corresponding increase in the number and quality of facilities. This makes the standard Biology laboratory apparatus unaffordable to most schools. Most secondary schools' facilities have, over time, been allowed to decay. This, in most cases makes secondary school teachers to skip activity-based learning and assessment of Biology practical students, thereby, creating a vacuum and a serious challenge to the 21st century educational needs of Biology learners. Therefore, P-SAT became a necessary alternative tool for classroom improvisation.

Purpose of the Study

Specifically, the study seeks to determine:

- i. The Content validity ratio of P-SAT

Research Questions

The following questions were raised:

- i. What is the content validity ratio of P-SAT?

The Concept of Validity

Validity expresses the degree to which a measurement measures what it purports to measure (Bolarinwa, 2015). An instrument is valid when it is measuring what is supposed to measure. In other words, when an instrument accurately measures any prescribed variable it is considered a valid instrument for that particular variable (Ghazali, 2016). Validity is questionably the most vital measures for test quality. The word validity tends to whether or not the test measures what it claims to measure. Validity is the amount of which an idea, deduction or measurement is well-originated and relates precisely to the real world. The term "valid" is resulting from the Latin word "validus" which means "strong". The validity of a measurement instrument is reflected to be the degree to which an instrument measures what it asserts to measure. Validity is usually employed in the context which explains the form of a test, purpose of a test, and the population for whom a test is proposed (ELHajjar, 2018).

Validation is an important process to ensure that the developed instrument is able to measure what it intends to measure. Validity also refers to the ability to predict specific events, or its relationship to measure other constructs based on the manner in which a scale was constructed (DeVellis, 2017; Ramli et al., 2020). Conventionally, validity is defined as the extent to which an empirical measure reflects the real meaning of the concept under consideration. It is the degree of correspondence between the purposes of the measurement and the purposes for which the test was designed. This is why it is especially important to clearly define the objectives of the test in the test specification, because this increases the possibility of achieving high validity of the test (Ivanova & Voynikova, 2021; McClure, 2022).

Content validity can be explained as how representative test items are in order to measure the behavior studied (Cohen & Swerdlik, 2018; Slaney, 2017). It can also be explained as the extent a test measures construct and the relevancy of the test to the aspects measured. Holistically, the content of the tests includes wording, format, and display of items. A test is considered content valid when the items relevantly measure the construct. Test experts and researchers who conduct content validity analysis should receive some constructive feedback for developing measurement tools. This constructive feedback can be provided by expert consensus that analyzes and evaluates the quality of measurement tools and objective criteria of the items. This feed-back forms the basis for revising tests or items, which upon finalization will be used for a pilot study. Thus, the test should have reasonably good psychometric properties, before being used in larger samples. The stages of content validation are explained below (Roebianto et al., 2023).

Relevance of CTT in Validity of Test

In classical test theory, any observed test score is a function of two hypothetical components: a true score and a random error. Mathematically, it is expressed as: $X = T + E$; where X is the observed test score, T is the true score of the individual, and E is the random error. The observed score is the score that is seen on the test paper. The true score is the expected value of the observed value of the observed score when the construct is measured repeatedly. The error score is the difference between a test takers observed score and his/her true score. This therefore means that it is the error that distorts the equalization of the true score and the observed score. The classical test theory considers two factors – content and item characteristics in developing test items (Hamleton et al. 1991 as cited in Bichi, 2016).

The content related issue is established with expert judgment of content relevance and representation. The other factor which considered item characteristics, focus on the difficulty level and the discrimination index of the items. Items that meet difficulty level index (0.30 to 0.70) and discrimination index (0.30 to 0.70 for standardized test) are kept in the item bank. Highly discriminating item is most desirable and level of difficulty depends on purpose for the test. For instance, a test for selection would have a high

difficulty index greater than 0.80. The focus of the classical test theory is to zero the error in a test score. These errors can be from sources such as content sources, and item sources (difficulty, discrimination and distracter), error due to reliability and bias (Gyamfi, 2022).

RESEARCH METHODS

This study employed the instrumentation research design. This design is also known as Research and Development design (R&D). The study was carried out in Bali, Jalingo and Wukari Education Zones in Taraba State, Nigeria. The population for this study is 15,142 from the 364 secondary schools in Taraba State. This comprised of all students in senior secondary school II (SS II) in public senior secondary schools in Taraba State. 8,392 of this population are males and 6,750 are females (Taraba State Ministry of Education, 2023). The sample size was 1,013 SS II students. Stratified purposive sampling technique was used.

P-SAT consisted of 162 multiple choice items with positive or negative stems. Each question has four distracters and one key. P-SAT was developed using Biology curriculum for senior secondary school students. Ecological Techniques with 55 items, Biological Instrumentation and Safety with 55 items, and Food and Digestive Enzymes with 52 items, were selected as the content areas for the development of P-SAT. This development was based on the table of specifications and Simpson’s levels of psychomotor domain (Simpson, 1972 as cited in Okeme 2015; Ukonze 2019). P-SAT was developed with levels which included Perception with 48 questions, Set with 18 questions, Guided Response with 14 questions, Mechanism with 19 questions, Complex Overt Response with 25 questions, Adaptation with 24 questions and Origination with 18 questions.

In order to establish content validity of P-SAT, ten experts who are experienced in the field of Biology were selected from Taraba State University Jalingo. These experts were given a copy of a 4-point rating scale. These experts were asked to rate their agreement to relevance of each item based on the study’s content areas, their ability to assess Biology skills and table of specification provided and Content Validity Ratio (CVR) was computed from the ratings. The study’s research objectives and a table of specification which conforms with Simpson’s levels of psychomotor domain were attached to the rating scales provided to each expert. This were provided to ensure that experts fully understood the study objectives and that the items were distributed according to Simpson’s levels of psychomotor domain as indicated in the table of specification. The rating scores generated were used to calculate the CVR for each item using Lawshe’s method which is mathematically illustrated as $CVR = (N_e - N/2) / N/2$, where N_e is the number of experts indicating the item is essential and N is the total number of experts.

PRESENTATION OF DATA

Research Question 1: *What is the content validity ratio of P-SAT?*

Table 1: Content Validity Ratio of P-SAT

Item	CVR	Remark									
1	.90	SA	41	1.00	PA	81	.90	SA	122	.90	SA
2	.80	MA	42	.80	MA	82	1.00	PA	123	1.00	PA
3	.90	SA	43	1.00	PA	83	.90	SA	124	1.00	PA
4	.90	SA	44	1.00	PA	84	1.00	PA	125	.90	SA
5	.90	SA	45	.90	SA	85	.90	SA	126	1.00	PA
6	.90	SA	46	.90	SA	86	.90	SA	127	.90	SA
7	.90	SA	47	1.00	PA	87	.90	SA	128	1.00	PA
8	.90	SA	48	1.00	PA	88	.90	SA	129	.90	SA
9	.90	SA	49	.90	SA	89	1.00	PA	130	1.00	PA
10	.90	SA	50	1.00	PA	90	.90	SA	131	.80	MA
11	.90	SA	51	1.00	PA	91	1.00	PA	132	1.00	PA
12	.90	SA	52	.90	SA	92	1.00	PA	133	.90	SA
13	1.00	PA	53	.90	SA	93	1.00	PA	134	1.00	PA
14	.90	SA	54	.90	SA	94	.90	SA	135	.90	SA
15	1.00	PA	55	.90	SA	95	1.00	PA	136	1.00	PA

16	.90	SA	56	1.00	PA	96	.90	SA	137	1.00	PA
17	.90	SA	57	1.00	PA	97	.90	SA	138	.90	SA
18	1.00	PA	58	.90	SA	98	.90	SA	139	1.00	PA
19	.90	SA	59	1.00	PA	99	1.00	PA	140	1.00	PA
20	1.00	PA	60	.90	SA	100	1.00	PA	141	.80	MA
21	.90	SA	61	1.00	PA	101	.90	SA	142	1.00	PA
22	1.00	PA	62	.90	SA	102	1.00	PA	143	1.00	PA
23	.90	SA	63	1.00	PA	103	.90	SA	144	.90	SA
24	1.00	PA	64	.90	SA	104	.80	MA	145	1.00	PA
25	1.00	PA	65	1.00	PA	105	.90	SA	146	.90	SA
26	1.00	PA	66	.90	SA	106	1.00	PA	147	1.00	PA
27	1.00	PA	67	.90	SA	107	.90	SA	148	1.00	PA
28	.90	SA	68	.90	SA	108	.90	SA	149	.90	SA
29	1.00	PA	69	1.00	PA	109	1.00	PA	150	.90	SA
30	1.00	PA	70	.90	SA	110	.90	SA	151	.90	SA
31	.90	SA	71	1.00	PA	111	1.00	PA	152	.90	SA
32	.90	SA	72	.90	SA	112	.90	SA	153	.90	SA
33	1.00	PA	73	.90	SA	113	.90	SA	154	.90	SA
34	1.00	PA	74	1.00	PA	114	.90	SA	155	.90	SA
35	.90	SA	75	.90	SA	115	.90	SA	156	.80	MA
36	.90	SA	76	1.00	PA	116	.90	SA	157	.90	SA
37	1.00	PA	77	.90	SA	117	1.00	PA	158	1.00	PA
38	1.00	PA	78	1.00	PA	118	1.00	PA	159	.90	SA
39	1.00	PA	79	1.00	PA	119	.90	SA	160	.90	SA
40	1.00	PA	80	1.00	PA	120	.90	SA	161	.90	SA
						121	1.00	PA	162	.90	SA

Keys: PA = Perfect Agreement, (All experts agree this item is valid)

SA = Strong Agreement (No major concerns)

MA = Moderate Agreement (Some experts found it less relevant; consider refining)

Table 1 revealed that most items have content validity index of 0.90 to 1.00. This indicated strong expert agreement on their relevance. The content validity index of P-SAT is therefore 0.93. A few items with item content validity index of 0.80 suggest they are still acceptable and relevant. The instrument demonstrates high content validity, as the majority of items meet the recommended content validity ratio threshold of 0.78.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings from this study revealed a very high content validity ratio of 0.93. This indicated that the items of P-SAT are acceptable and relevant. All 162 items of P-SAT met the cutoff ratio of 0.78 and are qualified for inclusion and are suitable for use. This is in agreement with one of the rule of thumb in Rutherford-Hemming (2018) which states that a CVR of at least 0.78 is necessary to deem an item or test as valid. These findings corroborated the findings Jalil et al. (2018) which revealed a content validity coefficient of 0.96 for 45 itemed I-KPS which was developed for measuring 6 (six) indicators of science process skills among high school students. This result was also consistent with that of Garba (2021) which performed content validation of its instrument, MSAI by 7 experts which establish a content validity ratio of 0.987 for tasks with 45 items along 6 sub-tasks developed from VTE minimum standard for NCE metalwork. This is however, inconsistent with PSMCT in Ombugus et al. (2019) where only 305 out of 316 skill items have content validity were considered suitable for inclusion in the psycho-productive test.

CONCLUSION

Results from this study revealed that P–SAT has a very high content validity ratio of 0.93. From the results of the expert rating, the study, therefore, concluded that P–SAT is a valid and reliable test capable of assessing practical skills of Biology students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this research paper, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Biology teachers in Taraba State should use P–SAT as a valid question bank for future assessment of practical skills among students in secondary schools across Taraba State.
- ii. School authorities, administrators and test experts should train and encourage teachers to make use of the procedure adopted in this study to enable them to carry out content validity analysis on test items to enable valid and reliable assessment of students.

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